

D2.6. Criteria for life cycle assessment

Authors Merlijn Morisse, Darren Wells, Pierre-Etienne Alary, Jean-Eudes Hollebecq, Clement Saint Cast, Michela Janni, Sven Fahrner, Roland Pieruschka, Stijn Dhondt

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Authors (Partner)

Responsible author	Name	Merlijn Morisse	Email	Merlijn.morisse@psb.vib-ugent.be
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Executive Summary

Objectives

The objective of EMPHASIS-prep is to develop a long term, distributed, pan-European infrastructure for state-of-the-art plant phenotyping experimental installations, which aims to improve crop performance to cope with climate changes and to keep pace with population growth. Plant researchers are required to test the improvement of plant and crop performance by using all categories of plant phenotyping infrastructures (as described in the deliverable D2.1. criteria list for plant phenotyping infrastructure) which can and should be combined together in a multiscale plant phenotyping approach, ideally, within a coordinated infrastructure, linked with an integrated data management system for storing and analyzing (meta)data, and with modelling platforms associated with the phenotyping platforms. To be able to form this distributed plant phenotyping infrastructure and understand the comparability and/or differences between installations, it is essential to map the new and existing plant phenotyping platforms that uses non-destructive, image-analysis based determination of the phenotype of plants and allow for a characterization of plant traits. This exercise of mapping the infrastructures has been performed and the results can be consulted in the EMPHASIS-PREP deliverable D2.3 mapping of existing and upcoming infrastructures. Deliverable D2.4, extensively describes the analyzing of the gaps and limitations based on the mapping activities. Moreover, where possible, the gaps will be strategically addressed to define how EMPHASIS could be helpful in the future to tackle these gaps in services towards excellence in plant phenotyping science within Europe.

Nevertheless, mapping and knowing the limitations of the European situation of the distributed infrastructure is not sufficient to understand the landscape of the experimental phenotyping installations in Europe and its financial impact. Knowing the life cycle of the installations, the time when updates and/or upgrades are needed and the life span before decommissioning of the installations, will complement the understanding of the operation of the installations and allow for planning and interaction between installations on a pan-European level.

Rationale

This deliverable, describes the analysis of life cycles of plant phenotyping experimental installations which will provide insights in when installations require updates, upgrades, in both software and hardware of the systems, or, as a last step in the life cycle, requires decommissioning.

The report summarizes surveys of the way life cycle is currently managed in plant phenotyping installations, in the 5 categories identified in D2.1., on the level of updates and upgrades on hardware systems, implementation of software systems, including an analysis of the financial situation of updates.

The results of the deliverable have been obtained by analysis of data from two sources: (1) interviews with 20 different installation managers of European plant phenotyping installations, within countries: The Netherlands, Belgium, France, UK, Germany, Italy and Czech Republic. All interviews have been added within the attachment of this deliverable. ; (2) Survey results of the 2021 survey of IPPN and EMPHASIS, with 396 participants of European origin.

During the lifecycle of an infrastructure the costs may vary substantially for example with respect to investment, operation or decommissioning. Within the main results we observe big differences between the different phenotyping categories (see D2.1 Criteria list), updates and upgrades on fields are almost nonexistent, whereas software tools need constant updates and controlled conditions need bigger upgrades every 5 to 10 years. Data about decommissioning was not easy to find as plant phenotyping, with automated systems, is a fairly new branch in plant science.

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The Plant Phenotyping infrastructures in Europe a life cycle assessment

Survey results on life cycle IPPN and EMPHASIS survey 2021

The 2021 survey of IPPN and EMPHASIS, had 396 participants of European origin and 690 participants globally. 126 of the global participants (75 of which were European participants) were in a professional position to provide information on the life cycle plans for their installations.

The inquiry shows that within the lifecycle of plant phenotyping installations it is estimated that the lifespan of an installation, from successful site-acceptance until decommissioning, is about 10 years on average, varying between 5 to 30 years. During this life cycle, these rather expensive technologies undergo updates and upgrades to keep pace with the rapid innovation of automation, computer vision and robotics. It is important to understand the difference between an update and an upgrade: to update means to bring something up to date, whereas to upgrade means to raise or improve something to a higher standard e.g. by adding new functionalities. In general plant phenotyping, using non-destructive automated often state-of-the-art installations, is a new approach with first installations established ten to fifteen years ago, and only about 19% of the European participants in the survey reported to have performed at least one update or upgrade on the installation after successful deployment of the system (see Figure 1). Of the participants outside Europe, this was 29%. Most updates are on the level of software (Europe 19%, outside Europe 29%), followed by upgrading parts of hardware (Europe 15%, outside Europe 20%), and the lowest percentage is the more expensive hardware additions, or upgrades (Europe 9%, outside Europe 16%).

Figure 1. Survey results on the assessment of upgrades and updates.

On the level of more substantial upgrades, see Figure 2, most upgrades are on the level of software (25% in Europe and 31% outside Europe), whereas, sensor replacements for new and better performing sensors are done 20% to 25% of the time. Also replacements of the sensors by similar sensors are done quite often, surprisingly more outside Europe than within Europe. It is noticed that automation upgrades on the level of carrier systems are done less frequently than the sensor upgrades. Possibly because the carrier systems are more rigid and less prone to innovation than the sensors particularly when considering the decreasing costs of optical sensors with high quality.

Figure 2. Survey results on the assessment on details of upgrades the installations

It's striking to notice that in general these results (figures 1 and 2) show that there are more updates and upgrades done on phenotyping installations outside Europe, compared to the installations in Europe. One explanation could be this reflects the funding schemes of Europe, and it's membership countries. Which probably are focused on investments on new state-of-the-art infrastructure without long-term vision on running the infrastructure for a reasonable life cycle.

In the life cycle assessment part of the survey was a question about cost models of updates and upgrades (see Figure 3). Surprisingly, a low number of answers were returned for this question (for both European and non-European participants more than 50% did not answer this question). It is possible that this question was unclear for the participants or they were not sure how to answer this question, or there were confidentiality issues with this question. Although it is clear from the data that only a low number of participants has a structured way of funding the updates and upgrades needed for the installations (10% of European and 4 % of non-European participants). Most of the updates are ad-hoc, if needed or if funds become available within a project. Life cycle plans for updates and upgrades are mostly not available in advance, which may provide some difficulties with respect to long-term sustainable operation.

Figure 3. Survey results on the assessment of cost models for life cycle.

Interviews of phenotyping installation managers: Life cycle in the different plant phenotyping pillars

A full life cycle assessment of plant phenotyping installations is very difficult and impossible to base on only the survey results. Survey questions could be interpreted differently and therefore result in inaccurate data. Moreover, scientists are less motivated to do long surveys with a lot of questions. To overcome this and to get a deeper insight into the life cycle, we decided to do interviews with phenotyping installation managers across Europe. Unfortunately this task became difficult because of the omission of physical networking meetings and conferences. Nevertheless, we were able to interview in total 20 installation managers from the Netherlands, Belgium, UK, France, Germany, and Czech Republic. With this data we learned that the life cycle of installations depends heavily on the plant phenotyping category.

1. Phenotyping installations in (semi-)controlled conditions for high-resolution and high-throughput Phenomics

Platform operators from a total of 16 active controlled environment phenotyping installations were interviewed between September 2020 and March 2021. Platforms were based in 5 countries (Belgium, UK, France, Germany, and Czech Republic). Platform age varied from 5 – 18 years

(Figure 4). The majority (81%) of the platforms had received a hardware update with a smaller majority (62.5%) receiving a software update. Hardware (either vectors or sensors or both) was upgraded between 1 and 10 years after commissioning, and software between 3 and 8 years. A minority of installations (44%) had a life cycle plan in place and fewer (38%) operated under a cost model for access (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Life-cycle assessments for controlled environment phenotyping platforms. (HW: hardware; SW: Software; orange dots: mean value)

Funding for decommissioning was estimated as being “high” for one platform, “low” for a minority (38%), but unknown for over half of the respondents (56%), reflecting the lack of a life-cycle plan in most cases. Funding for upgrades is mainly from institutional funding with some support from charges to industrial users.

2. Networks of lean field phenotyping and intensive field experimental sites for high throughput phenomics

Networks of (lean) field phenotyping are the oldest type of phenotyping installations, with most fields that started officially for research/phenotyping/breeding purposes by the early 1900's , depending on the age of the institute or company. If good agriculture management of a lean field is in place, including crop rotation and fertilising, the life cycle of such a field is without any upgrades and will in theory be able to continue over a long time. Of course some equipment for agriculture practices are needed to maintain the field, as for example tractors, plow, etc. but these are not considered as plant phenotyping material as such. Nevertheless, in the last decades a lot of high-tech equipment has been added to the fields to improve crop assessment and data interpretation,

as for example UAVs for imaging analysis, carrying different kinds of sensors and cameras, but also weather stations for metadata captation.

According to the interviews the life cycle of UAVs are reasonably short, with the batteries (maintenance) and sensors as limiting factors for life cycles. The average drone life cycle is about 5 years, before decommissioning, with a maximum of flight duration. This also depends on the overall quality of the brand. Most drones need regular replacement of smaller parts and upgrades on the software every 2 to 4 years. The sensors on drones are mostly for imaging purposes, which have reasonably high turn-over, which require upgrades every 4-5 years for RGB, multi and/or hyperspectral cameras.

Among the interviewees, there were also two managers of more intensive field phenotyping equipment, namely a rainout shelter system in Belgium and a BreedFACE system in Germany. The rainout shelter system is a rather rigid installation, and can have a lifespan of up to 30 years, if maintained properly e.g. every 4 years new plastic is needed (UV degradation of the plastic). The BreedFACE has a lower life span of about 10 years.

3. Modelling

In the context of plant science, modelling refers to the recourse to mathematical functions and equations to simulate processes, structure or functions of plants, canopies or organs. Due to the complexity of biological systems and the existence of multiple interactions at multiple scales (genes, pathways, cells, organs, whole plants, plant communities, plant-environment), modelling is a permanent exercise of identifying key and relevant processes, entities and scales that allow to explain the variability of traits or performance. Modelling and phenotyping are therefore synergistic in the sense that data produced in phenotyping installations are the raw material used in modelling to quantify and identify key processes, leading to improved understanding of dynamic biological systems, while modelling provides ways to compute non-measurable variables and enrich phenotype datasets.

The developers of eight models have been contacted in the context of the interviews. Seven of these models belong to the family of functional structural plant models (FSPM), that are closest to controlled conditions phenotyping. The last model belongs to the family of crop models that are closest to field phenotyping. The bias towards the first family is justified by the fact that the organisation of the crop model community is more advanced than that of the FSPM community. In

addition, the developer of the crop model is involved in large scale modeling initiatives and has therefore a broad view of the situation. One of the persons contacted also belongs to the phenotyping community.

At the time of the interview, a first release of the plant model database hosted at quantitative-plant.org website had been made public by EMPHASIS-PREP partners. The developers confirmed that their models (as well as other models that they use) were included in the database and that the information was up to date. Scientific papers are the main channel used by the modelling community to communicate about the production of new models and, in many cases, about the release of new versions. In many cases, and in line with the open source nature of plant models, many minor developments are made to released (and published) versions that may not be published.

In all cases, models are maintained by a permanent researcher. In general, the absence of a permanent researcher either leads to a progressive abandonment of the model, except if the model is routinely used by other groups that will keep it but may not be in a position to maintain it (e.g. keep the model compatible with future operating systems or hardware).

In most cases, the computer code of models is hosted on Github or on institutional repositories (e.g. gforge at INRIA), which does not mean that they are necessarily public. The case of models that are only available from the developer seems to be a minority. When models are developed in a modeling framework software (e.g. openAlea), they are often available as modules that are distributed with the framework. Models that are developed in such a framework are often easier to connect to other models developed in the same framework. The re-use of models is far from being a generality but is likely to be amplified in the next decade, in view of the development of new frameworks.

In most cases, modellers struggle to obtain clean and validated phenotypic datasets. One of them stated that often 50% of the project resources are dedicated to data fusion and cleaning. In the FSPM community, phenotypic data are mainly generated within the modeller's group. The connection between phenotyping groups and modelling groups works best when these belong to the same entity.

The structure of the phenotyping community in the context of EMPHASIS is therefore a huge opportunity, provided that EMPHASIS reaches the goal of making clean and validated datasets

easily accessible to external communities through automated search and distribution pipelines. The wider objective of engaging the phenotyping community in the world of modelling, however, seems to be a challenge at a much longer time scale and depends on the training of a new generation of researchers, so they come in closer contact with models to better understand the possibilities of simulations and predictions.

4. Data management systems

EMPHASIS aims to create centralized access to phenotyping data by building and integrating compatible, consistent information systems that will provide methods and interfaces for interoperability of datasets to manage, share, reuse and visualize heterogeneous, high-throughput plant phenotyping data stemming from different sources often in an interdisciplinary context.

FAIR data requires a proper identification system, if you want to gather data from various sources. Such an identification system would be easy if coming from a central service, but mostly requires the actors to agree on a common schema. This identification could for example be based on Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs), that is proposed in a sideway document Identification of objects with Uniform Resource Identifier (URI): recommendations for application in plant phenotyping available within the EMPHASIS community.

Data generated in large numbers still are sources of expenses. Even though it is increasingly cheaper, the amount of data generated is also bigger. Thus the life cycle of data is an important thing.

We can differentiate different types of data and the according treatment they should receive. The whole chain is described in the data management plan (DMP, see also Deliverable 4.5 Data Policy).

First of all the « raw data », that is the raw output of a sensor, or an image taken by drone, is typically refined using algorithms to generate more sophisticated data. This is the more frequent type of data and so the most costly to store. The nature of the data and the way to acquire it should be defined early, before the experiment begins. That is the first part of the DMP, the **planning**.

Because we are not always capable of **extracting** all the value out of the raw data, it is important to save them for later reuse. Planning is also foreseeing what we could do in the future that is not possible today.

We can see different strategies emerging from different places. The limit of 10 years is widespread because it is the data archiving time for all project data defined by EU and often nation funding agencies. Although, some others prefer 3 years, or 5 years. Obviously the data that are frequently reused will be stored longer.

After **processing** raw data we can call it « refined data ». This level is more valuable and the one to extract knowledge from. The different steps of processing are : validation, transforming, summarizing and integrating.

-**Validation** is the curation of outliers and missing values.

-**Transformation** is making data fit together with comparable format and units. Making sure the metadata is filled and ready for the next step of summarizing. This step is particularly important when the data are images. They require precise pre-treatments before running into image analysis.

-**Summarize** the data by creating variables and indicators by combining different levels of information and aggregating multiple data points into datasets.

-**Integrating** is combining different sources of information from different origins and age, data from 2 years ago as well as newly acquired data. This is a difficult part if the metadata is not well described, as combining different sources of information poses the problem of harmonization.

After all of these the **data analysis** can go, including visualization and statistics as well as modeling.

During this phase, it is important to keep track of different versions and provenance of the data as well as the algorithms. Hypotheses are confronted with data to be validated or invalidated. Conclusions are drawn and communication should be made, using the visualization tools best fitted.

In the end the goal is to **publish results** as well as **data** to allow future and further use of these data.

Among the different publishers we can find dataverse (<https://dataverse.org/>), that is meant to increase visibility of research data thus enhancing data citation. Some data repository such as e!DAL (<https://edal.ipk-gatersleben.de/>) focus on pushing FAIR data practices for data reuse. Another worth mentioning is FAIDare (<https://urgi.versailles.inrae.fr/faidare/>) that focuses mostly on referencing metadata and providing links to the appropriate data repository.

Storing data with proper indexation and metadata is not enough to promote data reuse. One should also adopt data standards early in the data life cycle. Multiple initiatives to promote some standardization helps researchers to find the best terms they need by browsing ontologies and connecting people to networks for exchanges on data practices. Research Data Alliance (<https://rd-alliance.org/>) is an actor that animates the community of data around the world. Other initiatives such as MIAPPE (<https://www.miappe.org/>) defines standards for minimum information for phenotyping experiments, BrAPI (<https://brapi.org/>) defines the data standards for exchanges between multiple sites.

This standardization is important to connect data of different sources. However we try not to limit the possibilities by linking the data and align the values. The Emphasis-Layer will mostly align concepts described in local database and not interfere too much on how the data is generated.

The quantity of initiatives towards a higher data reusability and interoperability extends the life cycle of data much further the original project or experiment generating them. And then should be taken into account before the **planning**.

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Conclusion, discussion and next steps

Plant phenotyping installations in Europe have a long history, mostly in field related phenotyping, but only in recent years have the infrastructures been improved enormously with technological advancements in robotics, AI and imaging. Most installations therefore are relatively new, less than 5 or 10 years old. The life-span of these installations, mainly the equipment, is estimated by the community to be approximately 10 years, but this depends on the category of installations with a range of between 5 and 30 years. Smaller equipment, such as sensors, need to be replaced in a shorter time-frame, and larger, more expensive technologies within greenhouses or the field, are often more rigid and have longer lifespans, but are often updated or upgraded to be functioning for a longer time. The major exception is software. Not only do the modeling installations and data management systems have a completely different life cycle, the software of the installations also requires very frequent updates, as e.g. for the cyber-security, or to properly function with new imaging code. Moreover, software needs to be adapted whenever a new sensor or technology is integrated in the system.

The life cycle of a data management system for plant phenotyping infrastructure is heavily dependent on the type of database. Most databases, if any existing in the institute, are fairly new. These are still in need of constant updating, which makes it difficult to assess the life cycle. Also, the life cycle of models depends heavily on the responsibility of the owner, mostly a permanent researcher at an institute. Updates will be performed whenever relevant to the research. Sometimes models are on sharing-platforms for open data such as Github, but this does not always mean that the code is accessible in a useful shape for any user. When models are developed in a modeling framework software (e.g. openAlea), they are often available as modules that are distributed with the framework. Models that are developed in such a framework are often easier to connect to other models developed in the same framework. The re-use of models is far from being a generality, but is likely to be amplified in the next decade, in view of the development of new frameworks. Data access is one of the major bottlenecks for modeling. The life cycle for data-storage is estimated around 10 years, and after this the data is mostly deleted. Nevertheless, the older data is still not findable. European initiatives within the framework of open data are a positive evolution to make data accessible. Also within EMPHASIS, both the EMPHASIS-layer as data and computation service will be a great step forward to establish better data and modeling life cycles.

Cost models for updates and upgrades are mostly not included in the funding plan of infrastructures. Updates and upgrades are mostly done ad hoc, and there are difficulties to find the resources for this. This is a phenomenon that has been observed across all categories of installations. It seems that some funding agencies have pick-uped on this, and some of them ask specifically for a cost model plan for any further updates and upgrades to be included in the proposal for new installations, which is unpredictable, but it is also unavoidable that upgrades will be needed within a rapidly evolving sector, to stay state-of-the-art.

Very few of the interviewed platform operators had plans in place for decommissioning or an idea of the likely costs. This is understandable in terms of the age of most phenotyping installations, but this will become more important as the current infrastructures age and reach end-of-life.

Glossary

API: Application Programming Interface

CAGR: Compound annual growth rate

Canopy: canopy is more than one plant - in CE setups this is the difference between a top-down camera imaging a stand of plants and a conveyor measuring plant by plant...

CSM: process-based crop simulation model

EMPHASIS: European Infrastructure for Multi-Scale Plant Phenotyping And Simulation for Food Security in a Changing Climate- ESFRI listed project

EMPHASIS-PREP: H2020 preparatory phase project of EMPHASIS

ENVRI: ENVRI is the community of the Environmental research infrastructures, projects and networks as well as other diverse stakeholders interested in the environmental research infrastructure matters

EOSC: European open science cloud

ERC=European Research Council

ESFRI: European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure

FACE: (Free-Air CO₂ Enrichment)

FAIR: findable accessible interoperable and reusable of digital assets

FSPM: functional-structural plant model

Installation: An INSTALLATION is the elementary level for data acquisition in a specific type of experiments. It stands for other frequently used terms such as 'platform', 'facility' or others.

KWS: The capital letters "K," "W" and "S" in the name KWS stand for Klein Wanzlebener Saatzucht, which means seed breeding from Klein Wanzleben.

Local infrastructure: A LOCAL INFRASTRUCTURE is a group of installations (see §1.3) located in one site depending on one institution (or more), which share governance committees, a common (or at least highly interoperable) information system, common principles for cost calculation and pricing and a common tool for user access.

PSI: Photo Systems Instruments

RGB: The RGB color model is an additive color model in which red, green and blue light are added together in various ways to reproduce a broad array of colors.

SEB: The Society for Experimental Biology

Shoot: phenotyping focusing on imaging

SPM: structural plant model

SQL database: Structured Query Language for databases

TB: in the context of data management systems: Terabytes

UAV: Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, mostly drones

URI: Uniform Resource Identifier

Web service: a layer of abstraction between the database technology and the user. This layer facilitates the interaction between user and provider.

WP: work package

Annex 1: Check list

Deliverable Check list (to be checked by the “Deliverable leader”)

	Check list	Comments
B e f o r e	I have checked the due date and have planned completion in due time	<i>Please inform Management Team of any foreseen delays</i>
	The title corresponds to the title in the DOW	<i>If not please inform the Management Team with justification</i>
	The dissemination level corresponds to that indicated in the DOW	
	The contributors (authors) correspond to those indicated in the DOW	<i>Please validate the Table of Content with your Activity Leader before drafting the deliverable</i>
	The Table of Contents has been validated with the Activity Leader	
	I am using the EMPHASIS deliverable template (title page, styles etc.)	
The draft is ready		
A f t e r	I have written a good summary at the beginning of the Deliverable	<i>A 1-2 pages max. summary is mandatory (not formal but really informative on the content of the Deliverable)</i>
	The deliverable has been reviewed by all contributors (authors)	<i>Make sure all contributors have reviewed and approved the final version of the deliverable. You should leave sufficient time for this validation.</i>
	I have done a spell check and verified the English	
	I have sent the final version to the WP Leader and to the Project coordinator (cc to the project manager) for approval	<i>Send the final draft to your WP Leader and the coordinator with cc to the project manager on the 1st day of the due month and leave 2 weeks for feedback. Inform the reviewer of the changes (if any) you have made to address their comments. Once validated by the 2 reviewers and the coordinator, send the final version to the Project Manager who will then submit it to the EC.</i>

